

DIGITAL PAYMENT SYSTEMS AND THE IMPACT ON EMPLOYMENT GENERATION: EVIDENCE FROM NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria continues to face persistent challenges with employment generation, marked by high unemployment and underemployment rates, especially among youth and in the informal sector. In response to the growing adoption of financial technology, this study investigated the impact of digital payment systems on employment generation in Nigeria from 2005 to 2023, using the Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) method. Time series data were obtained from the World Development Indicators (WDI) and the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin. The long-run findings show that mobile money transfers (MMT), ATM usage, point of sale (POS), and population growth had a positive effect on employment, with ATM, POS, and MMT statistically significant. In the short term, ATM, MMT, and population growth also significantly contributed positively, while POS was positive but not statistically significant. These results highlighted the pivotal contribution of digital payment systems in driving employment growth through increased financial activity and access. The study recommends targeted policy support to expand and formalize digital payment infrastructure to maximize employment gains.

Keywords: Digital payment systems, Employment generation, ARDL, Nigeria

JEL Codes: E42, G23, J21, O55

1. INTRODUCTION

In the evolving global economy, employment generation remains a key pillar of sustainable development and social stability. As the world transitions into a digital era, the integration of technology into financial services has reshaped the structure of labor markets and created new employment pathways. Particularly, digital payment systems, comprising mobile money platforms, point-of-sale (POS) services, internet banking, and fintech applications have become instrumental in expanding access to financial services, fostering entrepreneurial activities, and indirectly influencing labor absorption. With rising populations, especially in developing regions, the capacity to generate productive employment remains vital for poverty reduction and economic resilience (International Labour Organization, 2021; World Bank, 2022).

Globally, employment generation is not merely about the availability of jobs but also their quality, productivity, and contribution to inclusive growth. The benefits of employment generation transcend income stability; it promotes social inclusion, reduces inequality, and

supports consumption and aggregate demand (United Nations Development Programme, UNDP, 2021; Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, OECD, 2022; African Development Bank, AfDB, 2023). For countries to achieve sustainable development, the capacity to create jobs that match the skills of the labor force and respond to technological transformations is indispensable. Digital technologies have redefined the nature of employment, giving rise to platform-based work, remote employment, and digital entrepreneurship, all of which are strongly enabled by digital payment ecosystems (International Telecommunication Union, ITU, 2023; Nigerian Communications Commission, 2023; McKinsey & Company, 2023).

In Africa, employment remains a critical challenge despite being home to the youngest population globally, with over 60% of the continent's population under the age of 25 (AfDB, 2023; United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2022; World Bank, 2022). The continent needs to create approximately 12 million jobs annually to meet the demand from new labor market entrants, yet only about 3 million formal jobs are created each year (ILO, 2022; Brookings Institution, 2023). While traditional sectors like agriculture and extractives dominate employment in many African economies, the rise of digital finance presents new opportunities to integrate youth and informal sector workers into economically productive activities. In Kenya, for instance, the expansion of M-Pesa mobile money services led to the creation of over 185,000 new jobs between 2008 and 2015 (Suri & Jack, 2016; Consultative Group to Assist the Poor, 2018), demonstrating the job-creating potential of digital payment systems in African contexts.

Nigeria, Africa's most populous nation, continues to grapple with acute unemployment and underemployment. As of the fourth quarter of 2023, Nigeria's unemployment rate stood at 5.0% using the new methodology by the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) (NBS, 2024), but youth unemployment and underemployment remained disproportionately high, with over 13.5 million youths not engaged in any form of gainful employment (NBS, 2024; World Bank, 2023; ILO, 2023). The informal sector accounts for over 80% of employment in Nigeria, yet it is largely characterized by low productivity and limited access to financial tools that could boost income and job sustainability (AfDB, 2022; Enhancing Financial Innovation & Access, 2023). Structural issues such as poor infrastructure, inadequate access to finance, mismatched skills, and weak industrial base continue to hinder employment generation on a large scale (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2023; UNDP, 2023).

On the other hand, the digital payment systems offer a promising solution to Nigeria's employment problem by facilitating financial inclusion, supporting entrepreneurship, and enabling the growth of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The fintech sector in Nigeria, which grew by 200% between 2018 and 2022, has directly employed over 20,000 people and indirectly supported hundreds of thousands through agency banking and mobile money operations (CBN, 2022; Enhancing Financial Innovation & Access, 2023; McKinsey & Company, 2023). Figure 1 provides the details of some payment systems in Nigeria.

Figure 1: Some Payments System in Nigeria

Source: Central Bank of Nigeria, 2023

The volume of ATM transactions has been on a steady rise since 2009, with transactions growing from 109,161,646 in 2009 to 1,599,187,337 in 2021. It however dropped in volume to 1,506,991,903 in 2022 which might be because of using alternative channels. The volume of Point-of Sales (POS) transactions also grew rapidly from 918,256 in 2009 to 3,885,782,065 in 2022. This shows that the number of POS in Nigeria has increased than expected. Likewise, the mobile money transfer is not an exception as the volume also increased exponentially from 1,809,251 in 2009 to 1,861,362,984 in 2022 (National Interbank Settlement System, 2023; TechCabal, 2023; Statista, 2024). Based on the statistics provided by the Central Bank of Nigeria (2024), it is clear that the number of transactions carried out through POS machines is more than ₦18 trillion, with 1.5 billion transactions, while ATMs had 496 million transactions worth ₦12.2 trillion. Mobile money transactions have the highest number of transactions in digital payment systems, with over 7.18 billion transactions worth ₦78 trillion. This reflects the trend in the development of payment systems in Nigeria. These platforms not only provide income opportunities but also act as financial access points for the underserved, thus stimulating micro-business growth and improving local economies (PricewaterhouseCoopers, 2022; Alliance for Financial Inclusion, 2023; Ventures Africa, 2024).

However, digital payment systems have not significantly reduced unemployment in Nigeria because their impact is largely confined to improving financial transactions rather than creating substantial, long-term employment opportunities. These systems tend to automate processes rather than require large human workforces. While they have introduced new roles such as POS agents and mobile money operators, these jobs are often low-paying, informal, and lack job security or growth prospects. Additionally, the reach of these systems is mostly limited to urban centers, leaving rural populations, where unemployment is often highest underserved (CBN, 2023).

The Nigerian government has initiated several interventions to tackle unemployment, including the N-Power Programme, the Youth Investment Fund, and the Start-Up Act 2022 aimed at supporting digital entrepreneurship (Federal Ministry of Youth and Sports Development, 2023; CBN, 2022). However, implementation inefficiencies, policy inconsistencies, and funding bottlenecks have limited the effectiveness of these programs (CBN, 2023). The National Digital Economy Policy 2020–2030 was also introduced to promote digital inclusion and jobs

in ICT-related sectors, yet digital literacy and infrastructural deficits remain major obstacles, while unemployment in Nigeria keeps increasing (National Information Technology Development Agency, 2023; AfDB, 2023). It is against this background that this study examines the impact of digital payment systems on reducing unemployment in Nigeria. The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews relevant literature; Section 3 outlines the theoretical framework and methodology; Section 4 presents the empirical results and analysis; Section 5 discusses findings; and Section 6 concludes with policy implications and recommendations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Theoretical Review

The Job Creation and Destruction Model

The Job Creation and Destruction Model, by David J. Davis and John Haltiwanger in the early 1990s, considers the dynamic employment behavior in stressing the constant creation and destruction of jobs in response to occurrences like technological change, economic change, and firm dynamics (Davis & Haltiwanger, 1992). The model is rooted in the assumption that labor markets are characterized by continuous turnover in which technological advances, such as digital payment systems, create new jobs in newly emerging sectors but destroy existing jobs in traditional industries (Davis & Haltiwanger, 1992). Job creation is more likely to happen among young and smaller firms employing new technologies and old industries experiencing job destruction, ultimately resulting in re-allocation of jobs to newly emerging sectors (Haltiwanger et al., 2010). Critics contend that the model overlooks social job loss costs, including skills imbalances, geographical constraints, and economic disparities to movement of workers into new industries. It is also biased towards considering quantities of jobs and not quality, and most new jobs are of low quality or in the informal sector that can undermine the economy (Soskice & Iversen, 2000; OECD, 2017).

Despite these criticisms, in the instance of Nigeria's digital payment systems, this framework captures the way new employment opportunities are generated while traditional industries are replaced by innovations such as mobile money, POS systems, and fintech applications. Digital payments, for instance, have generated employment opportunities in Nigeria, where more than 1.8 million POS terminals have generated informal jobs for agents across both urban and rural areas (National Interbank Settlement System, 2023; TechCabal, 2023). The model further lays emphasis on labour market reallocation's role, calling on policies to encourage the development of skills and digital skills to equip employees to move into new technology-oriented jobs (Alliance for Financial Inclusion, 2023).

2.2. Empirical Review

Focusing on sub-Saharan Africa, Opoku-Okuampa (2024) explored the role of digital financial platforms, such as mobile banking, digital wallets, and online payment systems, in enhancing financial inclusion across the region. The findings demonstrated that digital financial services enhanced economic inclusion, which was linked to improved employment outcomes. Using data from the China Household Finance Survey, Ding et al. (2023) explored the mitigating effect of digital financial inclusion development on enhancing household entrepreneurship and alleviating poverty. The study found that digital financial inclusion significantly promoted household entrepreneurship, thereby contributing to poverty reduction. This comparative study by Liu et al. (2023) between eastern and western China investigated the influence of digital financial inclusion on urban–rural income disparity. Utilizing a static panel approach covering 22 provinces from 2011 to 2020, the research found that digital financial inclusion reduced income disparities, indirectly influencing employment opportunities.

Ekpo et al. (2023) examined the effect of electronic payment systems on the performance of the Nigerian banking industry between 2010 and 2019. Utilizing quarterly data and the ARDL method, the analysis revealed that mobile payment technology and POS usage had a positive, albeit statistically insignificant, impact on bank performance. Conversely, increased use of ATMs and web payment mediums showed an insignificant decline in bank performance. Utilizing microdata from 15,192 women across 29 African countries, Elouardighi and Oubejja (2023) employed Probit model estimation to examine the relationship between digital financial inclusion and women's labor force participation. The findings indicated that digital financial inclusion positively influenced women's participation in the labor force more than traditional financial channels.

Ovaga et al. (2023) carried out a study on the role of Point of Sale (POS) technology in job creation within Nsukka urban, Enugu State, Nigeria, from 2012 to 2021. Documentary and descriptive survey methods were employed to assess the impact of POS and mobile banking on small-scale businesses and youth unemployment. The results indicated that the introduction of POS technology facilitated financial inclusion, which allowed small businesses to grow and generate new employment opportunities. The study also found that POS adoption had significantly reduced youth unemployment, as numerous young individuals secured jobs as POS agents across various sectors of the economy. Austin-Olowo et al. (2023) examined the impact of digital financial services, including ATM, POS, WEBPAY, and mobile banking transactions, on the Nigerian economy. Using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression, the research analyzed the relationship between these digital financial services and Nigeria's GDP. The findings indicated a positive impact, suggesting that the use of digital financial services can stimulate economic growth and potentially create employment opportunities.

The study by Andrea et al. (2022) assessed the impact of electronic payment systems (e-payment) on the GDP of Nigeria. The ARDL model was employed to analyze time-series data spanning several years. The findings revealed that e-payment systems, including ATM, POS, and mobile applications, had a significant and positive effect on Nigeria's GDP. Tiatité and Adama (2022) examined the effects of financial inclusion on employability in 32 sub-Saharan African countries. Employing fuzzy set theory and binary probit models, the study found that a 10-percentage point increase in financial inclusion raised the probability of employment by 4.4 percentage points.

Adewole (2022) investigated the impact of the adoption of Point of Sale (POS) technology on employment generation in Nigeria, covering the period from 2009 to 2021. Using the Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique, the findings suggested that POS adoption has a positive and significant effect on employment creation, particularly in the low-skilled job segment. The results also showed that POS systems have contributed to the growth of small businesses, further enhancing job creation in both urban and rural areas. Yang and Geng (2022) analyzed panel data from 29 Chinese provinces spanning 2011 to 2018 to assess the impact of digital financial inclusion on employment structure optimization. Employing fixed effects and two-stage least squares (2SLS) models, the research found that digital financial inclusion significantly improved employment structures, particularly in eastern China. Adewale et al. (2022) examined the effect of POS business on employment generation in Nigeria. Covering the period from 2009 to 2021, the study utilized the ARDL technique. From the findings, it was found that POS adoption had a significant positive effect on employment creation and contributed to an increase in low-skilled job opportunities. However, it did not have a significant impact on the proportion of employment relative to the population.

Analyzing Nigeria's data from 1981 to 2019 using the ARDL method, Nteegah (2021) concluded that financial inclusion reduced unemployment in the short term. The findings indicated that deposit penetration, credit penetration, and domestic investment penetration negatively and significantly impacted the unemployment rate, suggesting improved employment outcomes. Efang et al. (2020) empirically investigated the impact of electronic payment systems on Nigeria's economic growth from 2009 to 2018. Specifically, the ARDL model indicated that ATM usage had a significant positive impact on RGDP, while POS and web payments also contributed positively, though not significantly.

Adeoye and Tosin (2020) conducted a study to examine the influence of electronic banking on employee retention in Nigerian banks using staff from Guaranty Trust Bank as the sample population for the study. The study utilized a descriptive research design in collecting data using questionnaires, while the Spearman's rho correlation to test the relationship between electronic banking and employee retention, while binary logit regression was used to test the influence of electronic banking on employee retrenchment. The results indicated a significant relationship between electronic banking and employee retention, and also showed that electronic banking has a significant influence on employee retrenchment.

Takon et al. (2019) examined the contribution of digital payment systems to the efficiency of the banking sector in Nigeria, using quarterly data from 2009 to 2018. The study employed OLS and ECM regression, the findings showed that digital payments, had a negative and significant impact on bank efficiency in both the long and short run. However, digital payments positively contributed to non-interest income, return on equity, and return on assets in Nigerian banks. Adebisi et al. (2013) investigated the factors influencing the adoption of mobile payment systems in Nigeria. The study conducted a survey with 227 respondents in Lagos and neighboring areas. The findings revealed that while Nigerians recognize the benefits of mobile payments, such as convenience and reduced transaction times factors like interface complexity, trust in service providers, security concerns, and cost significantly affect adoption rate.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Theoretical Framework

The model is based on the framework of job creation and destruction theory of Steven J. Davis and John Haltiwanger in the early 1990s. The model views employment dynamics as a continuous process of job creation and job destruction, fueled by technological change, as well as the entry and exit of firms and structural economic adjustments. It argues that technological innovations do not merely destroy jobs, but reallocate labour across firms and sectors. With regards to this study, digital payment systems such as POS, ATM, and MMT are viewed as technological innovations that have the potential of restructuring employment patterns in Nigeria. Their expansion may reduce routine banking roles while creating new opportunities in fintech services, agent banking, ICT support, and digital entrepreneurship. Importantly, the theory emphasizes firm-level and sectoral turnover, which is consistent with how digital finance expands through new entrants, platform-based services, and evolving business models. This makes it more suitable than static employment theories because it explains both the displacement and the emergence of jobs within a transitioning economy. Thus, the model provides a suitable theoretical basis for examining how digital financial innovation influences employment generation in Nigeria.

3.2. Model Specification

Based on the job creation and job destruction theory which form the theoretical foundation of this study, this study adapts and modifies the model of Adewole et al. (2022). The model was

adapted because some of the variables of this study were included in their model and they are good in explaining the relationship between digital payment systems and employment generation in Nigeria. The model is expressed as;

$$EMP = f(POS, SKE, POP) \quad 1$$

Where, EMP is employment rate, POS = point of sales, SKE = skilled employment, POP = population. This study therefore incorporates POS, ATM, mobile money transfer, and population growth as the variables that explain employment generation in Nigeria. The functional form of the model is specified in Equation 2.

$$EMP = f(POS, ATM, MMT, POP) \quad 2$$

Where, EMP = Employment generation; POS = point of sales; ATM = automated teller machines; MMT = mobile money transfers; POP = population growth

The model can be expressed econometrically as in Equation 3.

$$EMP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 POS_t + \beta_2 ATM_t + \beta_3 MMT_t + \beta_4 POP_t + \mu_t \quad 3$$

The model can be expressed as logarithm so as to be able to interpret the coefficients as elasticities. This is specified in Equation 4.

$$\ln EMP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln POS_t + \beta_2 \ln ATM_t + \beta_3 \ln MMT_t + \beta_4 \ln POP_t + \mu_t \quad 4$$

Where, t-1 is the lagged value of the variables; *ln* = natural logarithm; μ_t is the stochastic error term which explains other variables that cannot be captured in the model; β_0 to β_4 are the slopes of the coefficients.

3.3. Model Justification and Theoretical Linkage

Digital payment systems represent technological shocks within the financial sector. POS, ATM, and MMT are included as proxies for digital financial expansion. The POS measures agent banking and financial activities of merchants, which can create self-employment. ATMs represents banking automation, where technology replaces human labor and generates technical employment. MMT stands for fintech penetration and digital transaction intensity, which affects overall employment opportunities through financial inclusion. Population is included as a control variable to capture labor supply and market size effects. These variables are measured using the data from the deployment numbers and transaction volume/value from the Central Bank of Nigeria, thus providing consistency in the theoretical expectations and empirical operationalization.

3.4. Data Analysis Techniques

This study employed the ARDL technique as a method of analysis. This method estimates the model's long- and short-term dynamics even with mixed order of integration such as I(0) and I(1). Similarly, when the sample size is small, it also yields estimates that are more accurate. To do this, we checked the consistency and objectivity of our estimations utilizing the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) unit root test. To determine whether the variables are related over the long term, the ARDL bounds test was also employed. Following the Pesaran et al. (1999) specifications, the model is given as;

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \ln EMP_t = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln EMP_{t-1} + \beta_2 \ln POS_{t-1} + \beta_3 \ln ATM_{t-1} + \beta_4 \ln MMT_{t-1} \\ & + \beta_5 \ln POP_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_1 \Delta \ln EMP_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_2 \Delta \ln POS_{t-1} \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_3 \Delta \ln ATM_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_4 \Delta \ln MMT_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_5 \Delta \ln POP_{t-1} \\ & - \emptyset ECM_{t-1} \\ & + \mu_t \end{aligned}$$

5

Description, Measurement and Sources of Data

Variables	Description and Measurement	Sources of Data
Employment Generation	It reflects the proportion of the working-age population that is gainfully employed, measured as an employment-to-population ratio.	World Development Indicators (WDI) 2023
Point-of-Sales	POS refers to the location at which a payment of a card transaction occurs, usually by way of a device such as a credit card terminal or cash register. It is measured in volume.	CBN Statistical Bulletin 2023
Automated Teller Machines	It is a cash point that can be used to withdraw cash, do transfers by using debit card or credit card at the machine. The variable’s volume is used as measurement.	CBN Statistical Bulletin 2023
Mobile Money Transfer	It is a digital device that allows banking transactions to be made through a mobile device, such as a cellular phone or a smart phone. The variable is measured in volume	CBN Statistical Bulletin 2023
Population Growth	This is the growth rate of citizens living in Nigeria, which is measured in millions of people	WDI 2023

Source: Researchers’ Compilation, 2025

3.5. Nature of Data

The data collected are annual time series data.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1. Results Presentation and Interpretation

4.1.1. Pre-estimation Results

Stationarity Test

Table 1: ADF Unit Root Test

Variables	ADF Stats	Critical Value @5%	Order of Integration
EMP	-4.2239	-3.0522	I(1)
POS	-3.1538	-3.0656	I(0)
ATM	-8.8068	-3.0810	I(0)
MMT	-8.0187	-3.0810	I(0)
POP	-9.7660	-3.0404	I(0)

Source: E-views 13 Output.

The result of the ADF test indicated that employment generation was stationary at first difference while other variables such as POS, ATM, MMT and POP were stationary at levels. These showed mixed order of integration which made bounds test a necessary test for cointegration.

Table 2: Lag Selection Criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-64.63910	NA 195.9724	0.001579	7.737677	7.985003	7.771780
1	82.34021	*	2.34e-09*	5.815579*	4.331626*	5.610962*

Source: E-views 13 Output.

The result from the lag selection shows that the optimal lag length of the model is 1, as it is shown by Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) with the lowest absolute value. This implies that incorporating one lagged value reflects an appropriate balance between model complexity and goodness of fit.

Table 3: Test for Cointegration

Test Statistic		Value				
F-statistic		4.889500				
		10%	5%			
			1%			
Sample Size	I(0)	I(1)	I(0)	I(1)	I(0)	I(1)
30	2.525	3.560	3.058	4.223	4.280	5.840
Asymptotic	2.200	3.090	2.560	3.490	3.290	4.370

* I(0) and I(1) are respectively the stationary and non-stationary bounds.

Source: E-views 13 Output.

From the result on Table 3, the F-statistic is 4.8895, which is higher than the 5% significance level's upper critical value of 3.49. This signifies that there is a substantial long-term correlation among the variables. Consequently, ARDL-ECM regression was performed.

4.1.2. Estimation Results

Table 4: Long-run Estimates

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
<i>EMP(-1)*</i>	-0.298482	0.232726	-1.282545	0.2356
<i>ATM(-1)</i>	0.588130	0.545347	2.729041	0.0021
<i>POS(-1)</i>	0.192197	0.102896	3.717143	0.0007
<i>MMT(-1)</i>	0.930048	3.452096	2.661565	0.0068
<i>POP(-1)</i>	0.727797	0.497588	0.248920	0.8097
<i>C</i>	-446.0176	1285.734	-3.346897	0.0076

Source: E-views 13 Output.

The long run result revealed that the lagged value of employment generation has negative and insignificant impact on its current value. The coefficient value is -0.2984 and it implied that 1% increase in the previous value of EMP caused a decline of 0.29% in its current value. The coefficient values of ATM, POS, MMT and POP further revealed that these variables increased employment generation by 0.59%, 0.19%, 0.93% and 0.73% respectively. Amongst these variables, ATM, POS and MMT were statistically significant.

Table 5: Short-run Estimates

Dependent Variable: D(EMP)

Method: ARDL

Sample: 2006 2023

Included observations: 18

Max. dependent lags: 1 (Fixed)

Fixed-lag linear regressors: ATM POS MMT POP

Deterministics: Restricted constant and no trend (Case 2)

Selected model: ARDL(1,1,1,1,1)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
<i>COINTEQ*</i>	-0.298482	0.056235	-5.307789	0.0001
<i>D(ATM)</i>	0.530109	0.313960	4.118528	0.0012
<i>D(POS)</i>	0.849065	4.172195	0.203506	0.8419
<i>D(MMT)</i>	0.111589	0.530623	3.148422	0.0077
<i>D(POP)</i>	0.249235	0.302536	5.425477	0.0001
<i>R-squared</i>	0.787587	Mean dependent var		1.522222
<i>Adjusted R-squared</i>	0.722229	S.D. dependent var		5.944977
<i>S.E. of regression</i>	3.133239	Akaike info criterion		5.352145
<i>Sum squared resid</i>	127.6234	Schwarz criterion		5.599470
<i>Log likelihood</i>	-43.16930	Hannan-Quinn criter.		5.386247
<i>F-statistic</i>	12.05038	Durbin-Watson stat		1.606153
<i>Prob(F-statistic)</i>	0.000259			

*p-values are incompatible with t-Bounds distribution.

Source: E-views 13 Output.

The short run ARDL results indicated a strong and statistically significant relationship among the variables, as evidenced by the error correction term (COINTEQ*) coefficient of -0.2985, which is negative and highly significant ($p = 0.0001$), confirming stability and convergence toward equilibrium at a moderate speed of approximately 29.85% per period. Also, a 1% increase in ATM, MMT, and POP led to increases in employment generation by approximately 0.53%, 0.11%, and 0.25% respectively. These variables all have positive and statistically significant impacts, as their p-values (0.0012 for ATM, 0.0077 for MMT, and 0.0001 for POP) are below the 0.05 significance threshold. However, POS, with a coefficient of 0.8491, shows a positive but statistically insignificant effect ($p = 0.8419$), suggesting that 1% increase in POS increased employment generation by 0.85% but not significant. The R-squared value of 0.7876 indicated that about 78.76% of the variation in the dependent variable was explained by the model, and the adjusted R-squared of 0.7222 still reflected strong explanatory power. The F-statistic of 12.0504 with a p-value of 0.0003 confirmed that the model is jointly statistically significant. Meanwhile, the Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.6061 suggested that the model is free from autocorrelation.

4.1.3. Post-Estimation Tests

Table 5: Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test

F-statistic	1.926184	Prob. F(2,6)	0.2259
Obs*R-squared	7.038168	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.0696

Source: E-views 13 Output.

This finding implied that the model has no serial correlation because the probability F-statistic of 0.2259 is higher than 5% level of significance.

Table 6: Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

Null hypothesis: Homoskedasticity

F-statistic	0.986986	Prob. F(8,9)	0.5019
Obs*R-squared	8.411868	Prob. Chi-Square(8)	0.3943
Scaled explained SS	2.200142	Prob. Chi-Square(8)	0.9743

Source: E-views 13 Output.

The F-statistic from the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey heteroskedasticity test is 0.987 with a corresponding p-value of 0.5019. This test evaluates whether the variance of the residuals from a regression is constant (homoskedasticity) or varies across observations (heteroskedasticity). Since the p-value is greater than 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis of homoskedasticity. This means there is no significant evidence of heteroskedasticity in the model, indicating that the variance of the residuals is constant and the model's estimates are efficient and reliable.

Test for Stability

Figure 1: Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) Test
Source: E-views 13 Output

Figure 2: Cumulative Sum of Square (CUSUM of Squares) Test
Source: E-views 12 Output

The results from Figures 1 and 2 show that the residuals stay within the 5% significance boundaries, indicating that the model is stable over time. This means there are no structural breaks or major changes in the relationship between variables, confirming the reliability and consistency of the model’s estimates.

4.2. Discussion of Findings

These findings align with the theoretical expectation that increased access to digital financial services facilitates greater financial inclusion, business efficiency, and market expansion, all of which can stimulate employment. Specifically, the positive and significant impact of ATM usage on employment is consistent with the studies by Efang et al. (2020) and Andrea et al. (2022), which reported that ATMs contribute positively to Nigeria’s economic performance and, by extension, employment. Similarly, Tiatité and Adama (2022) found that improvements in financial inclusion, often driven by ATM and mobile technology significantly raise employment probability, reinforcing our model's outcomes. The significance of mobile money transfers also aligns with Opoku-Okuampa (2024), who found that mobile banking and digital wallets enhanced economic inclusion and improved employment outcomes across sub-Saharan

Africa. Ding et al. (2023) further support this view, demonstrating that digital financial inclusion drives household entrepreneurship and poverty alleviation in China—both of which are critical pathways to job creation. The positive and significant impact of MMT on employment in our model conforms with these findings, suggesting that Nigeria, like other developing economies, benefits from mobile financial services as engines of employment growth. In contrast, the positive but statistically insignificant impact of POS in our model diverges from some micro-level studies such as Ovaga et al. (2023) and Adewole (2022), which emphasized the role of POS technology in reducing youth unemployment and promoting small-scale enterprise growth in Nigeria. However, it aligns with macro-level analyses by Ekpo et al. (2023) and Efanga et al. (2020), which found that although POS systems have the potential to enhance performance and employment, their statistical effect remains weak due to market informality, scalability issues, or underutilization. This mixed evidence suggests that while POS may indeed facilitate localized employment, especially in the informal sector its broader, quantifiable impact on national employment figures is less robust.

Furthermore, our model's findings are in harmony with Nteegah (2021) and Takon et al. (2019), who showed that financial inclusion and digital payments indirectly support employment through improved economic indicators like reduced unemployment and increased non-interest income in banks. The observed relationship in our study supports the view that digital payments are crucial in driving employment indirectly through improved access to financial services and increased business activities. Finally, the model's results conform to the findings of Austin-Olowo et al. (2023) and Adewale et al. (2022), who identified a positive link between digital financial services and economic growth. As employment generation is a key channel through which economic growth materializes at the micro-level, the positive coefficients in our model reflect expected outcomes.

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The empirical findings indicate that ATM deployment, mobile money transactions, and population growth have statistically significant effects on employment generation, while POS terminals do not show a significant impact. Therefore, the results suggest that not all digital payment instruments contribute equally to job creation in Nigeria. The strong positive impact of ATM usage and mobile money transfer captures the way electronic financial infrastructure exposes more individuals to financial services, particularly to previously unbanked and underserved groups. By facilitating faster, safer, and more efficient transactions, such systems lower entry costs for small and medium-sized enterprises, increase entrepreneurial activity, and increase the ease of doing business. Improved access to finance stimulates business expansion, raises transaction volumes, and is a source of demand for labour, especially in the informal and small-scale economy. Mobile money services, for example, empower micro-entrepreneurs and offer decentralized employment opportunities, while ATM infrastructure needs operational support, technical maintenance, and security personnel. Although, POS usage showed a statistically insignificant effect in the model, whatever micro-level evidence exists indicates that it still has an important role to play in local-level employment, particularly among youth in urban and semi-urban areas. The results affirm that electronic payment systems are not just instruments of financial efficiency, but also catalysts for inclusive economic participation and employment growth.

In line with the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made;

- i. Since ATM plays an important role, measures can be adopted by the Central Bank of Nigeria to enhance ATMs' penetration, particularly in rural and semi-urban areas.

- This can generate jobs directly in machine installation, maintenance, and security and affect employment indirectly with better access to cash for small and medium enterprises.
- ii. With mobile money transfer also having a significant positive impact, policies that promote mobile money adoption by expanding network infrastructure, lowering transaction fees, and collaborating with telecoms and fintechs should be formulated and implemented by the CBN. Mobile money agents, service providers, and supporting businesses can provide jobs, especially for youth and women.
 - iii. While POS has no statistically significant impact, it is still a broad channel of informal employment. To facilitate its impact, there must be enabling support by the CBN for formalization, training of POS operators, and improved access to credit and startup capital. This will help transform POS services into a sustainable source of livelihood from a subsistence-level activity.

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